

**KNOWLEDGE
WITHOUT
BOUNDARIES**

eifl 2025
ANNUAL
REPORT

WHERE WE WORK

In 2025, EIFL worked in partnership with library consortia in 36 countries. We have also run projects in an additional 24 countries where we do not have library consortia.

■ **PARTNER COUNTRIES** are countries where we have a formal agreement with the national library consortium. EIFL partner consortia work with all EIFL programmes.

■ **PROJECT COUNTRIES** are countries in which we have worked with libraries on specific projects.

WHERE WE WORK

EIFL works in collaboration with libraries in 60 developing and transition countries.

AFRICA Angola, Botswana, Côte d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Morocco, Namibia, Mozambique, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania, Togo, Tunisia, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe **ASIA PACIFIC** Cambodia, China, Fiji, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Laos, Maldives, Mongolia, Myanmar, Nepal, Thailand, Uzbekistan **EUROPE** Albania, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Georgia, Hungary, Kosovo, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine **LATIN AMERICA** Chile, Colombia **MIDDLE EAST & NORTH AFRICA** Palestine, Sudan, Syria.

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**OUR VISION IS A WORLD IN
WHICH ALL PEOPLE HAVE THE
KNOWLEDGE THEY NEED TO
ACHIEVE THEIR FULL POTENTIAL.**

Photo by Ghana Library Authority.

WHO WE ARE

EIFL (Electronic Information for Libraries) is an international not-for-profit organization that works with libraries in developing and transition countries to enable access to knowledge for education, learning, research and sustainable community development.

Our strategy has three goals:

To advance a fair and sustainable transition from paywalled to open access (OA) content

Major achievements in 2025 —

- By the end of the year, 15 agreements with publishers were in place enabling authors from EIFL partner countries to publish for free or at reduced prices in OA in 2,927 journals. 2,945 articles were published in OA in 2025. Savings in Article Processing Charges amounted to US\$6,345,895.
- To increase the availability of OA content, we published a new model provision on secondary publication rights (SPR) in the EIFL Draft Law on Copyright, and promoted SPR as efficient policy and legal instruments for making articles available in OA via repositories.
- We contributed to strengthening Diamond OA journal publishing in Africa, Europe and Latin America. Diamond OA is a scholarly communications model in which journals do not charge fees to either authors or readers —
 - We awarded 16 grants to strengthen the efficiency, quality and sustainability of over 100 Diamond OA journals in nine countries in Africa.
 - Created training courses and useful resources for Diamond OA publishers: 13 courses available on the European Diamond Capacity Hub; guides such as 'Quality in Diamond OA Publishing'; 'Generative AI in Diamond Open Access Publishing'; 'Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) Guide for Journals', and 'Optimise your operations: Guide for Diamond Open Access Publishers'.

- Launched Diamond OA publishing communities of practice in Africa and Europe.

To support research, teaching and learning

Major achievements in 2025 —

- We continued to negotiate agreements with publishers for free or affordable pricing for paywalled e-resources. By the end of 2025, 84 commercial e-resources from 24 vendors were available through EIFL, including journals, e-books, reference works and aggregated databases covering a broad range of subject areas.
- We advocated for national copyright law reform to encourage the adoption of modern copyright laws that maximize access to content. We participated in copyright law reviews in Armenia, Malawi, Moldova, Uganda and Ukraine.
- We contributed to ending the book famine for persons with print disabilities by supporting ratification and domestication of the Marrakesh Treaty in Kenya, Lesotho, Nigeria and Maldives.
- We advocated for an enabling policy environment to support open and reproducible research. As a result of our policy work, two national (Estonia and Uganda) and eight institutional (Latvia, Serbia and Ukraine) open science policies were adopted.
- We supported the creation and maintenance of open public infrastructures that enable the publication and sharing of research in OA journals and repositories:

- Helped to improve the quality of services of 82 OA journals in Africa, Armenia, Ukraine and Uzbekistan, and five repositories, including three national repositories in Armenia, Georgia and Myanmar.

- Organized 10 webinars on best practices in using Open Journal Systems journal management software and four webinars for repository managers.

- We strengthened open science training:
 - Continued monthly virtual meetings of the EIFL Open Science Trainers Community of Practice, which now has over 80 trainers from 20 EIFL partner countries.
 - Co-facilitated two OpenAIRE open science train-the-trainer bootcamps.
 - Developed useful resources for trainers, including the 'EIFL Digital Research Literacy Training Programme Outline for Librarians' (third edition).
- We launched a campaign to promote the registration of research organizations with ROR (the Research Organization Registry) for accurate recognition and attribution of research, and developed the EIFL guide 'How to check whether your organization has a ROR ID and get one if it doesn't'.

To foster digital transformation of public library services

- We continued to build training, facilitation and digital skills of public librarians in Ghana as part of the 'Digital learning @ Ghana public libraries' project. By the end of 2025 —

- Thirty trained public library staff from 15 regional and branch libraries managed by the Ghana Library Authority had provided digital literacy training to over 11,300 students. Skills learnt included word processing, graphic design, coding, web development, misinformation and online safety.

- We advocated with governments and the private sector in Ghana, Malawi and Zambia for resourcing of public libraries with digital technology:
 - In Ghana we organized two partnership-building events for Government officials and other stakeholders to present the results of the Digital learning @ Ghana Libraries project.
 - In Malawi the Ministry of Information and Digitalisation allocated 40 computers to 17 branches of the National Library Service.
 - In Zambia, Airtel Zambia donated 26 wireless routers with two months' unlimited data to 20 public libraries.
- We continued to produce online learning material for public librarians, including six more short videos in the EIFL-PLIP 'Small Bites' series, on the topics library project development and organizing library training.
- To advance innovation in public libraries, we selected four libraries (China, Colombia, Croatia and South Africa) to receive the 19th EIFL Public Library Innovation Award. The award recognized exceptional STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, the Arts and Mathematics) programmes.

DIRECTOR'S REPORT

The year was full of activities to support no-fee open access publishing. No-fee, also known as Diamond, open access publishing directly advances our mission of expanding access to knowledge. By removing financial barriers for both readers and authors, Diamond open access ensures that research is freely available to anyone, anywhere in the world.

With new funding from the European Commission for the ALMASI ('Aligning and Mutualizing Nonprofit Open Access Publishing Services Internationally') project, we were able to extend our collaboration with the Latin American Diamond open access publishing community. With our partners, we mapped the nonprofit publishing initiatives and services, and policy and funding models for Diamond open access publishing, in three continents (Africa, Europe and Latin America). During the year we proactively engaged with over 100 Diamond open access journals in Africa and also conducted numerous webinars and produced a variety of practical guides and training courses to support journal editors and communities of practice in Europe and Africa.

While negotiating with publishers for waived or discounted Article Processing Charges (APCs) to make publishing in open access affordable for authors in our partner countries, we observed that publishers were less willing to offer APC waivers. This tendency makes our work in strengthening Diamond open access publishing and open repositories, and the promotion of Rights Retention strategies and Secondary Publication Rights as efficient policy and legal instruments for making articles available in open access, even more important.

We have fostered an enthusiastic community of open science trainers, and in this report

we feature our contribution to open science training and the work that members of this community are doing in their countries.

While we built researchers' open access publishing, open data and open science skills, we also advanced basic ICT skills of school students. In Ghana, public librarians trained by EIFL built the digital and information literacy skills of over 11,300 students aged from 12 to 18, enabling them to use the internet meaningfully, safely and confidently.

Thank you to everyone — our partners, our funders, board members and staff — and we look forward to working with you in 2026.

RIMA KUPRYTĖ, DIRECTOR

OPENING UP ACCESS TO RESEARCH

How EIFL's training helps advance open science

PhD candidates at the 9th International PhD
Summer School, held in June 2025, by Kaunas
University of Technology in Lithuania.
Photo by Jonas Klėmanas.

“What I especially like about EIFL’s training and resources, is how they marry open science theory with practical skills. Open science can sometimes be very abstract. But EIFL’s training makes it practical and interesting.”

– EGLĖ JUODĖ, INFORMATION MANAGER AT THE DEPARTMENT OF SCIENTIFIC INFORMATION AND DATA AT VILNIUS UNIVERSITY, LITHUANIA

To support research, teaching and learning, EIFL advocates for an enabling policy environment for open science, the establishment of open public infrastructures for the publication and sharing of research in open access (OA), organizes train-the-trainer activities and develops resources to support open science training.

Open science is an approach that makes research processes and data open and transparent at all stages of the research, from planning to dissemination of results. It has become widely recognized as contributing to better and more efficient science and innovation. Major European research funders, like the European Commission (EC), and growing numbers of national research funders now mandate or encourage open science for the research they fund. In 2021 EIFL took part in drafting the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, and contributed to the toolkit developed to facilitate implementation of the Recommendation. As a result of these developments, the need for open science training surged.

EIFL began conducting OA publishing training in 2004, and has steadily expanded training to include a broader range of open science skills and competencies — for example, research data management and sharing and other digital research skills.

Since 2017 EIFL has focused on training open science trainers in Europe (as part of EC-funded projects) and in EIFL partner countries. We led the training in two major European open science initiatives, the FOSTER project and OpenAIRE, and participated in the EOSC Future, DIAMAS and ALMASI projects as course developers and trainers.

We organized webinars on open science topics and skills, week-long online and in-person bootcamps, and developed resources to support open science trainers. A particularly well used resource was the *EIFL Research Literacy Training Programme Outline for Librarians*, and we published a third edition in 2025. In 2024 we began building a Community of Practice (CoP) for open science trainers in our partner countries that today counts over 80 members. We host monthly meet-ups for CoP members to share training experiences and support each other.

We asked open science trainers from EIFL’s network to share their experiences of providing open science training in their countries.

OPEN SCIENCE TRAINING IS MAKING ITS MARK IN ETHIOPIA, GHANA AND ZIMBABWE

Getnet Lemma Tefera is a professional librarian at Addis Ababa University (AAU) Libraries and a lecturer at AAU. He is also EIFL OA Programme Coordinator for the Consortium of Ethiopian Academic and Research Libraries (CEARL), EIFL’s partner library consortium in Ethiopia.

Getnet recalls EIFL’s long-term partnership with CEARL, dating back to 2008, and involving several projects. Among these projects was the development of a three-module open science course that is still being used for training of researchers, PhD students and librarians in CEARL member institutions.

AAU Libraries provides researcher training twice a month. “The training is usually related to open science — research data management (RDM), archiving data and articles in OA repositories, and publishing in OA journals. Mostly, our learners are early career researchers. On average we have 200–300

students per session. Training can be longer than two hours, and for practical sessions we use the computer lab. We also regularly provide training for librarians and research administrators, because they are the people who support the science community.”

Open science training is making its mark, said Getnet. “These days, you can meet any researcher and start a discussion on open science, and they can engage. In the past, some researchers were hesitant to publish in OA because they thought the quality was poor. Through our training and awareness-raising, this has changed.”

“Through EIFL’s training we learnt about the importance of data repositories for sharing research data. We drafted a policy that was approved by the university, that tasked AAU Library to conduct RDM training for AAU research grant recipients. Archiving is increasing, and we now have over 500 datasets and 57 dataverses in the AAU Research Data Repository.”

In Zimbabwe, **Josiline Chigwada** is University Librarian at Chinhoyi University of Technology (CUT) and also serves as EIFL OA Programme Coordinator in Zimbabwe. In addition to providing open science training for faculty and students at CUT, Josiline organizes and conducts training for the 20 member institutions of the Zimbabwe University Libraries Consortium (ZULC), EIFL’s partner library consortium.

“In the early years, our concern was the establishment of institutional OA repositories and OA publishing. Through a project with EIFL (2005) we established an institutional repository at the University of Zimbabwe. This was the first in the country and today, after much advocacy,

awareness-raising and training, all ZULC member universities have institutional repositories. Our focus is now more ensuring that the repositories are well used, and our training for faculty, students and librarians also includes RDM.

“As part of my own learning I regularly attend the EIFL CoP open science trainers’ meet-ups. Engaging with open science trainers from other countries is very useful for me. During the discussion people share best practices and what has worked for them; challenges and how they have dealt with them. So if you look at it from the Global South perspective, most of us are facing the same challenges and solutions will be similar too.”

Richard Bruce Lamprey, College Librarian at the College of Science at Kwame University of Science and Technology (KNUST), is EIFL Country Coordinator in Ghana, and also regularly attends meetings of the EIFL CoP for open science trainers.

“The meet-ups provide opportunities to learn new training methods, from trainers in different countries. I have had valuable input into how to motivate senior researchers to practice open science, how to advocate with managers for institutional support, and approaches for integrating open science into policies and academic curricula.”

An experienced open science trainer, Richard has provided training, mostly for early career researchers and PhDs at KNUST, on OA and responsible publishing; research quality and journal evaluation; grant writing with open science compliance; reference management tools, and AI and research. In addition, Richard provides introductory open science training during annual induction courses that are mandatory for newly-hired university staff. “We

train about 100 new staff a year, and as they get into their jobs, they come back for further open science training,” he said.

POLICIES DRIVE OPEN SCIENCE TRAINING AT KAUNAS UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY AND VILNIUS UNIVERSITY IN LITHUANIA

Eglė Juodė, Information Manager at the Department of Scientific Information and Data at Vilnius University (VU), and **Marjan Monshi**, a data manager at Kaunas University of Technology (KTU) library and PhD candidate at the Institute of Materials Science at KTU, conduct open science training for faculty and students at their universities. Both are active participants in the EIFL CoP for open science trainers and regularly attend the monthly meet-ups.

In 2022, VU adopted an open science policy, and followed up with a policy implementation plan in 2023 that makes VU Library responsible for providing open science training. The April 2025 update of KTU's open science policy includes mandatory Data Management Plans (DMPs) for PhD students. In addition, in 2025 the Research Council of Lithuania (RCL) made open publishing of articles and data mandatory for all RCL-funded research.

All these developments have escalated the demand for open science training.

Eglė estimates that VU library's Department of Scientific Information and Data trains an average of 500–1,000 people a year, with requests coming from all directions. “Requests can come from the top, for example, the university management asked us for training on the RCL requirements. Sometimes the need comes from researchers, for example if I get questions on the same topic over and over, I organize training on that topic. We also train and set assignments involving open science for many PhD candidates.

“When I started working at the library, I did not even know what open science was. I learnt a little bit from everywhere, from conferences, videos on YouTube. I used resources from the FOSTER open science website, OpenAIRE and EIFL.

“Through participating in the EIFL CoP meet-ups for open science trainers I learnt how to make my online training interactive. A training session on data management led by Milica Ševkušić (EIFL OA Programme Project Coordinator) stands out. Both her outlook and the way she structured training were inspiring. I now plan training using her structure, and I often use Mentimeter (an interactive training tool that engages learners), especially with PhDs.”

Marjan learnt her open science skills while completing an RDM course for PhDs that KTU Library developed with support from EIFL. “It was through this course that I began my open science journey,” said Marjan. “For the first time, I wrote a DMP and learnt how to properly store, manage and share my research data.”

Marjan wanted to be involved in tasks related to open science because she understood its relevance. When the KTU Library announced that it was looking to hire a data manager to join its team, Marjan applied and was hired for the position. The library also engaged her in training researchers. “To learn more about open science, I joined the OpenAIRE train-the-trainer Bootcamp. This event was transformative — we learnt the theory and practice of open science, and also how to train researchers.

“Now, for me, the most important space for learning about training is the EIFL CoP open science trainers meet-ups. The participants are from different countries in Europe and Africa, and we openly discuss the challenges we are facing, and share solutions and best practices. I also share resources that I receive from the meet-ups with the librarians and the other data managers at KTU. One of the most useful resources is the *EIFL Digital Research Literacy Training Programme Outline for Librarians*.

“Inspired by the collaborative spirit of the EIFL meet-ups, we have activated our Open Science Community at KTU with monthly meet-ups with researchers,” said Marjan.

COMMUNITY DRIVEN OPEN SCIENCE TRAINING IN SERBIA

In Serbia, there is an informal but well-organized community of 70–80 open science trainers,

mostly consisting of research librarians. Two energetic contributors to this community are **Ljiljana Radisavljević**, Librarian at the Institute for Vegetable Crops, and **Obrad Vučkovic**, Head of Library Services and Repository Manager at the Vinca Institute of Nuclear Science, University of Belgrade. In addition to providing open science training in their institutes, Obrad and Ljiljana train nationally in Serbia and both have trained at regional and international open science training events organized by EIFL. They are also regular participants in the EIFL CoP meet-ups of open science trainers.

The informal trainers' group in Serbia provides a safe environment for younger or less experienced trainers to practise their training skills, give presentations to more experienced trainers, and receive suggestions for improvement.

“I cannot say enough how important the connection with EIFL is. I feel much closer to people doing the same thing all over the world,” said Ljiljana.

Both Obrad and Ljiljana emphasised the importance of the resources created or co-created by EIFL in their training. “EIFL develops resources with the real-world constraints faced by trainers in less wealthy countries in mind, helping the trainers to deliver high-quality training despite limited funding and staff capacity,” said Obrad.

In 2024 the government of Serbia adopted the Open Science Platform 2.0, which updates the original 2018 policy. The policy mandates OA to all publications and research data resulting from publicly-funded research, and requires institutions to align with these principles.

“After that, our open science training became more dynamic; researchers would bring practical questions to training, for example, ‘We are about to publish, what can we do to make it open science?’ and we would work with them to find solutions,” said Ljiljana.

FACTS ABOUT EIFL OPEN SCIENCE TRAINING

FROM 2004 TO 2025

374,300+

people trained in open access, open data and open science

1,500+

training events organized and led

100+

open science trainers in EIFL's network in Africa, Asia and Europe

70+

countries in Africa, Asia and Europe reached

23

bootcamps organized / co-organized for open science trainers

FROM 2023 TO 2025

18,800

views of EIFL open science resources

16,700

views of webinar recordings

4,400

downloads of EIFL open science resources

MEET THE PEOPLE

Using knowledge to change their lives and the lives of others

Photo by Augustinas Zukovas.

GIFTY SEY

MUNICIPAL LIBRARIAN, EFFUTU LIBRARIES GHANA

As head of Effutu Libraries in Ghana's Central Region, Gifty Sey manages a network of 19 branch public libraries. Gifty frequently visits schools to engage students in digital reading and other digital skills programmes that the libraries offer. "I also train staff in the branch libraries, and they are also conducting digital skills classes in their local schools," she says.

Effutu Municipal Library is one of 15 regional and municipal libraries taking part in the Digital learning @ Ghana public libraries project, implemented by EIFL and the Ghana Library Authority.

"Before the project, we were running very low scale digital skills programmes, teaching basic skills limited to the school curriculum — Word, Excel, PowerPoint, how to type — in just a few schools. Now we are reaching out to more schools, with an expanded range of skills and knowledge.

"EIFL introduced us to free and open online tools that we use to build the children's skills — like Canva (graphic design), Rangers (coding), web development software and interactive reading apps. We have classes on recognizing misinformation and disinformation online, and about online safety," says Gifty.

"The children especially love the reading apps because they make reading fun by correcting punctuation, and with quizzes and spelling tests. We have just a few tablet computers that we bring to schools, and after school hours, the children rush to the library to make sure they are first in the queue to continue to read," says Gifty.

By the end of 2025 the Digital learning @ Ghana public libraries project had trained 30 librarians from the 15 libraries, who built digital literacy skills of over 19,000 Junior and Senior High School students in short outreach visits to schools and in-depth workshops in libraries.

Photo by Ghana Library Authority.

"The training and digital equipment we received through the project have transformed the work of our libraries, and improved digital literacy and online safety skills of thousands of children."

– GIFTY SEY

MARIANA HARJEVSCHI

**DIRECTOR, B.P. HASDEU MUNICIPAL LIBRARY
MOLDOVA**

In 2003, Mariana Harjevschi was nominated by REM — Electronic Resources for Moldova Consortium — to serve as EIFL’s Copyright Coordinator in Moldova. Mariana had recently begun working in Moldova’s first public library specializing in law, and through training and mentorship from EIFL, she quickly developed a knowledge of copyright issues.

Mariana also organized the translation into Romanian of EIFL resources on copyright, such as EIFL’s Handbook on Copyright and Libraries and the Copyright for Librarians curriculum, so that librarians throughout Moldova could benefit (the curriculum was incorporated into library and information science programmes at Moldova State University).

Under Mariana’s leadership, REM actively engaged with AGEPI (the State Agency on Intellectual Property) during copyright law reviews. As a result, copyright law amendments adopted in 2011 and 2022 contain many positive library provisions. “I am passionate about ensuring that copyright acts as a force for good in Moldova. We value our relations with AGEPI in developing practical solutions to the legal challenges that libraries face in digitizing material, managing databases and introducing new digital research tools.”

In 2026, the copyright law is set to change again as Moldova readies itself for EU membership. Mariana’s knowledge, leadership and experience will help to ensure that the new law aligns with the best of European legislation to benefit education, research and digital inclusion, as the country looks towards a new future within an enlarged European Union.

“Strong copyright exceptions and limitations are necessary for freedom of expression, democratic engagement, education and community development, and librarians are well placed as effective advocates for the public interest.”

– MARIANA HARJEVSCHI

STEVEN SEBBALE

HEAD OF HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT, UGANDA NATIONAL COUNCIL FOR SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY UGANDA

When Steven Sebbale joined the Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST) in 2009 as a research intern, open science was just starting to be known in Uganda. In 2023, as Head of Science Policy he led the development of an open science policy that was formally adopted by the UNCST Board in 2025 following an extensive and participatory stakeholder engagement process.

“We sincerely appreciate EIFL’s invaluable expertise and financial support throughout this process. Your partnership was instrumental in enabling UNCST to convene multiple consultative workshops with researchers, policy makers, institutional leaders and civil society stakeholders from across Uganda. These engagements have ensured that the policy reflects the diverse voices and priorities of our national science and innovation ecosystem,” said Steven.

UNCST regulates, monitors and evaluates all aspects of science, technology, and innovation (STI) in the country; translates STI policies into regulations and standards to guide the operations of the entire STI system; and provides continuing professional development for researchers.

As the national clearing house for research, UNCST plays a key role in reviewing, and registering research proposals to ensure that they meet ethical and scientific standards. “On average, we review about 1,800 to 2,500 research projects annually. These projects are now required to be carried out in compliance with the UNCST open science policy,” said Steven.

“The open science policy positions UNCST as a leader in championing open science practices, fostering greater accountability, collaboration and innovation within Uganda’s research landscape.”

– STEVEN SEBBALE

TOLGONAI KOZHOKANOVA

ELECTRONIC SERVICES LIBRARIAN, AMERICAN UNIVERSITY OF CENTRAL ASIA KYRGYZSTAN

EIFL began working with the Kyrgyzstan Library Information Consortium (KLIC) in 1999.

In 2021 Tolgonai Kozhokanova was nominated by KLIC to serve as EIFL Licensing Coordinator for Kyrgyzstan. In this role, Tolgonai has different responsibilities.

“My main role is to inform consortium member libraries about the availability of EIFL-negotiated e-resources. I encourage and help our members to promote and use these e-resources. I act as a bridge between EIFL and KLIC members — if a member has difficulty with subscriptions or licensing, I can ask the licensing team at EIFL to advise,” says Tolgonai.

Over 50 KLIC member institutions subscribe to e-resources negotiated by EIFL. In 2025, KLIC members were eligible to subscribe to 40 EIFL-negotiated e-resources from eight publishers, at no cost, including e-book collections, journals and online databases. Since Tolgonai’s appointment as EIFL Licensing Coordinator, the number of subscribers and the usage of these e-resources has grown steadily.

“EIFL also negotiates free and discounted Article Processing Charges (APCs) for authors to publish articles in open access, and I make sure that these opportunities are promoted too. After a series of webinars that we organized with EIFL in 2025, our researchers have become more aware about EIFL’s open access publishing agreements,” says Tolgonai.

In 2025 authors in Kyrgyzstan published 39 articles in fully open access journals of seven publishers, compared to 14 articles in journals of five publishers in 2024. In 2025, authors and institutions saved US\$81,825 through APC waivers and discounts.

“Being a member of EIFL is a great benefit for academic libraries. Free access to e-resources from international publishers significantly supports our researchers and scholars. Very few universities in my country have budgets to subscribe to foreign e-resources.”

– TOLGONAI KOZHOKANOVA

OUR NETWORK

EIFL partner library consortia nominate coordinators who serve as the main point of contact between EIFL's Programmes and their consortium. In their countries, they lead and facilitate activities initiated by EIFL, and have been central to our success and achievements over the years.

Many thanks to our Country Coordinators, Licensing Coordinators, Open Access Coordinators and Copyright Coordinators for their enthusiasm and hard work in 2025.

ALBANIA

Consortium of Albanian Libraries

Country Coordinator: Albana Velianj
Licensing Coordinators: Renata Bardhi and Mirlona Buzo
Open Access Coordinator: Renata Bardhi

ARMENIA

Digital Library Association of Armenia (DLAA)

Country Coordinator: Anna Chulyan
Licensing Coordinators: Tatevik Tamazyan
Copyright Coordinator: Hasmik Galstyan
Open Access Coordinator: Tigran Zakaryan

AZERBAIJAN

Azerbaijan Library & Information Consortium for Availability of Electronic Information (AzLIC)

Country & Licensing Coordinators: Jamila Yusifova and Iltifat Ibrahimov
Copyright Coordinator: Adila Abdullayeva

BOTSWANA

Botswana Libraries Consortium (BLC)

Country & Licensing: Coordinator: Naniki Maphakwane
Copyright Coordinator: Khutsafalo Kadimo
Open Access Coordinator: Poloko Ntokwane

CHINA

Library Network of the Chinese Academy of Sciences

Country Coordinator: Xiwen Liu (until April)
Country Coordinator (from April), Open Access & Copyright Coordinator: Kunhua Zhao

CONGO

Consortium des Bibliothèques Académiques du Congo (COBAC)

Country Coordinator: Eliezer Mwangane
Licensing Coordinator: Jean Baptiste Unen

CÔTE D'IVOIRE

Consortium des Bibliothèques de l'Enseignement Supérieur de Côte d'Ivoire (COBES-CI)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Cécile Coulibaly
Copyright Coordinator: Ahou Marie-Claire Allou Ouffouet
Open Access Coordinator: Adjoh Hortense Kakpo Epse Outtara

ESTONIA

Consortium of Estonian Libraries Network (ELNET)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Marika Meltsas
Copyright Coordinator: Karmen Linask
Open Access Coordinator: Elena Sipria-Mironov

ETHIOPIA

Consortium of Ethiopian Academic and Research Libraries (CEARL)

Country Coordinator: Girma Aweke
Licensing Coordinators: Bedassa Motuma Beyene and Girma Aweke (from May)
Copyright Coordinator: Ato Yoseph Bizuneh
Open Access Coordinator: Getnet Lemma

FIJI

Fiji Library Consortium

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Udy Shukla

GEORGIA

Georgian Integrated Library Information System Consortium (GILISC) 2017

Country, Open Access & Copyright Coordinator: Nino Pavliashvili
Licensing Coordinator: Marika Zhorzholiani

GHANA

Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries in Ghana (CARLIGH)

Country Coordinator: Richard Bruce Lamptey
Licensing Coordinator: Mac Anthony Cobblah
Copyright Coordinator: Teresa Adu
Open Access Coordinators: Donyina Fokuo and Nana Tuhufo Quagraine

KENYA

Kenya Libraries and Information Services Consortium (KLISC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Arnold Mwanzu
Copyright Coordinator: Paul Gichohi
Open Access Coordinator: Stanislaus Agava

KOSOVO

Consortium of Electronic Libraries in Kosovo (CELK)

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Bukurije Haliti

KYRGYZSTAN

Kyrgyzstan Library Information Consortium (KLIC)

Country Coordinator: Jyldyz Bekbalaeva
Licensing, Copyright & Open Access Coordinator: Tolgonai Kozhokanova

LATVIA

National Library of Latvia

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Ilze Linde (until December)
Copyright Coordinator: Inta Mikluna (until November)

LESOTHO

Lesotho Library Consortium (LELICO)

Country Coordinator: Buhle Mbambo-Thata
Copyright Coordinator: Pontso Nkuebe
Licensing Coordinator: Tahleho Tseole
Open Access Coordinator: Matseliso Kabeli

LITHUANIA

Lithuanian Research Library Consortium (LMBA)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Jevgenija Sevcova
Copyright Coordinator: Janina Marcinkeviciene
Open Access Coordinator: Gintare Tautkeviciene

MALAWI

Malawi Library and Information Consortium (MALICO)

Country Coordinator: Patrick Mapulanga
Licensing Coordinator: Trevor Namondwe
Copyright Coordinator: Blessings Katuma
Open Access Coordinator: Chifundo Chipendo

MALDIVES

Maldives Library Consortium (MLC)

Country Coordinator: Zulhana Adam
Licensing Coordinator: Majidha Ali

MOLDOVA

Electronic Resources for Moldova (REM)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Elena Tudor Railean
Copyright Coordinator: Mariana Harjevschi
Open Access Coordinator: Natalia Cheradi

NAMIBIA

Namibia Library Consortium (NALICO)

Country Coordinator: Hedwich Meyer
Licensing Coordinator: Namutenya Hamwaalwa
Copyright Coordinator: Victoria Isaacks

NEPAL

Nepal Library and Information Consortium (NeLIC)

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Jagadish Aryal

NORTH MACEDONIA

Macedonian e-Libraries (MEL)

Country, Licensing, Copyright & Open Access Coordinator: Miodrag Dadasovic

PALESTINE

Palestinian Library and Information Consortium (PALICO)

Country Coordinators: Diana Sayej Naser; Rami Alhindawi for Gaza
Licensing Coordinator: Mohammad Abu Hamdieh
Open Access Coordinator: Asad Tom

SENEGAL

Consortium des Bibliothèques de l'Enseignement Supérieur du Sénégal (COBESS)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Mandiaye Ndiaye
Copyright Coordinator: Awa Diouf Cisse
Open Access Coordinators: Djibril Diallo, Abdoulaye Gueye and Mangaty Sakho

SERBIA

Serbian Library Consortium for Coordinated Acquisition (KoBSON)

Country Coordinator: Tatjana Timotijevic
Licensing Coordinators: Tatjana Timotijevic and Boris Denadic
Copyright Coordinator: Dragana Milunovic
Open Access Coordinator: Milica Sevkusic

SLOVENIA

Consortium of Slovene Electronic Collections (COSEC)

Country Coordinator: Karmen Stular Sotosek
Licensing Coordinator: Herman Erculj (until September)
Open Access Coordinator: Alenka Kavcic-Colic (until May), Natasa Jordan (from June)

SUDAN

Sudanese Academic Libraries Consortium (SALC)

Country Coordinator: Iman Abdelrahman
Licensing Coordinator: Entsar Abbas Ebraheem Mohamed
Copyright Coordinator: Wahbi Abdalrahman
Open Access Coordinator: Babelshafia Makki

TANZANIA

Consortium of Tanzania Universities and Research Libraries (COTUL)

Country & Open Access Coordinator: Paul Samwel Muneja
Licensing Coordinator: Cyrill Ndekakao

THAILAND

Electronic Information for Libraries in Thailand (EIFL-Thailand)

Country, Copyright and Licensing Coordinator: Soeythip Sukul
Open Access Coordinator: Adisak Sukul

UGANDA

Consortium of Uganda University Libraries (CUUL)

Country Coordinator: David Bukenya
Licensing Coordinator: Florence Nambooze
Copyright Coordinator: Bosco Apparatus Buruga
Open Access Coordinator: Drake Tamale

UKRAINE

Association 'Information Consortium'(until May); New consortium under construction

Country, Copyright, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Oleksii Vasyliiev (until June)
Country Coordinator: Tetyana Yaroshenko (from June)
Licensing Coordinator: Olena Rachynska (from July)

UZBEKISTAN

EIFL Uzbekistan Consortium

Country Coordinator: Husniya Boysunova
Licensing Coordinator: Alisher Kattabekov (until September), Behbudshoh Anvarov (from October)
Open Access Coordinator: Gulbakhor Kabiljanova

ZAMBIA

Zambia Library Consortium (ZALICO)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Eness Chitumbo
Copyright Coordinator: Benson Njobvu
Open Access Coordinator: Pilate Chewe (until October)

ZIMBABWE

Zimbabwe University Libraries Consortium (ZULC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Nyarai Chibanda
Copyright Coordinator: Mildred Gwangu
Open Access Coordinator: Josiline Chigwada

OUR TEAM

The EIFL General Assembly (GA) 2025 took place in Yerevan, Armenia, from 30 September to 2 October. The GA brings together delegates from our network of library consortia, representatives of our partners in the publishing industry, the EIFL Management Board and staff.

STAFF

Andrius Kriščiūnas, Finance Manager

Britt-Marie Wideberg, Licensing Programme Manager

Edvaldas Baltrūnas, Public Library Innovation Programme Coordinator

Iryna Kuchma, Open Access Programme Manager

Jean Fairbairn, Communications Manager

Jevgenija Ševcova, Programmes and Events Coordinator

Milica Ševkušić, Open Access Programme, Project Coordinator

Ramunė Petuchovaitė, Public Library Innovation Programme Manager

Rima Kuprytė, Director

Teresa Hackett, Copyright and Libraries Programme Manager

Ugnė Lipeikaitė, Public Library Innovation Programme Impact Manager

MANAGEMENT BOARD

Emilija Banionytė, Chairperson, Vilnius County Adomas Mickevičius Public Library, Lithuania

Anna Chulyan, Digital Library Association of Armenia; National Library of Armenia (from July)

Colleen Campbell, Max Planck Digital Library, Max Planck Society, Germany

David Bukenya, Uganda Christian University

Jyldyz Bekbalaeva, American University of Central Asia, Kyrgyzstan (until July)

Marjan Vernooy-Gerritsen, retired, former Programme Manager for IT & Research at SURF, The Netherlands

FINANCIAL REPORT

EIFL FINANCES 2025

INCOME, CARRY FORWARD, RESERVES	€	%
• Programme income	809,565	26.9%
• Participation fees	59,310	2.0%
• General Support Funds and Reserves	2,110,298	70.1%
• Sponsorship, interest and other income	31,930	1.0%

Total 3,011,103

EXPENDITURE	€	%
• Programme delivery	1,092,864	90.1%
• Personnel & contracted expenses	84,534	7.0%
• Operating expenses	35,124	2.9%

Total 1,212,522

COMMITTED EXPENDITURE FOR 2026–2029 PROGRAMME DELIVERY GENERAL SUPPORT FUNDS AND RESERVES 1,798,581

OUR FUNDERS

ORGANIZATIONS

We would like to thank the following organizations for their generous support for our work in 2025:

- Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation
- European Commission Erasmus+ Programme through Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine
- European Commission Horizon 2020 Framework Programme through OpenAIRE AMKE
- European Commission Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)
- Internet Society Foundation through TechSoup Global
- Open Society Foundations
- Luxembourg Development Cooperation Agency (LuxDev)
- Wellcome Trust

EVENTS

In 2025, EIFL organized, supported or took part in 138 events, workshops and conferences about issues that affect access to knowledge.

JANUARY

- Kyrgyzstan Science Communication Week (Online)
- ALMASI project kick-off meeting (Madrid, Spain)
- Public Launch of the ALMASI project and the European Diamond Capacity Hub (Madrid, Spain)
- No-fee OA publishing in Africa Community of Practice meeting (Online)
- Open science trainers meet-up (Online)
- DIAMAS Conversation: DIAMAS Toolsuite and Guidelines for Diamond Open Access publishing (Online)
- Webinar: OJS: Multilingualism, migration and metadata harvesting
- European Rights Retention Community of Practice meeting (Online)
- EIFL Public Library Innovation Award Ceremony (Panevežys, Lithuania)

FEBRUARY

- UiT The Arctic University of Norway webinar: Journal policy on generative AI
- INELI-Egypt Convention (Online)
- Webinar: Repository set-up and management best practices
- 17th Berlin Open Access Conference (Berlin, Germany)
- OASPA webinar: What do we mean by quality in open access publishing?
- CoARA Community Consultation on the CoARA report: 'Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment: Principles and Framework' (Online)

- No-fee OA publishing in Africa Community of Practice meeting (Online)
- Webinar: OJS in OA scholarly publishing
- Digital Learning @ Ghana Public Libraries project knowledge-sharing meeting (Accra, Ghana)
- Webinar: Maximising the Benefits of Repositories for Research Institutions
- Paper Pledge for the Planet progress meeting (Online)
- Open science trainers meet-up (Online)
- Webinar: Embedding repositories in your research workflows

MARCH

- Webinar: OJS: Experiences from the University of Zambia; XML conversion
- International Open Data Day: Ukraine (Online)
- Webinar: Open Access, Open Science, Open Data: modern trends & challenges
- Webinar: Workflows and day-to-day jobs for repository managers
- No-fee OA publishing in Africa Community of Practice meeting (Online)
- Webinar: OJS: Best practices from Lithuania and South Africa
- Open science trainers meet-up (Online)
- Consortium of Ugandan University Libraries webinar: Copyright and Ethical Issues in Research

APRIL

- Diamond OA journal management and sustainability workshop (Online)

- WIPO Copyright Committee (46th Session) (Geneva, Switzerland)
- Navigating the Open Science Landscape: From Theory to Practice workshop (Paola, Malta)
- No-fee OA publishing in Africa Community of Practice meeting (Online)
- Regional webinar on OA scholarly publishing (Online)
- Open science trainers meet-up (Online)
- Webinar: Increasing visibility of OA journal content with OJS and DOAJ
- DIAMAS Conversation: Applying the DOAS — insights from early adopters (Online)
- EIFL-PLIP T-break: Libraries for Africa Digital Futures (Online)

MAY

- Maldives Library Consortium meeting (Online)
- Conference of the Association of Lithuanian Municipal Public Libraries (Nida, Lithuania)
- 18th eLearning Africa Conference (Dar es Salaam, Tanzania)
- COMMUNIA Salon: Unfair licensing practices (Online)
- COAR Annual Conference: Trends in Policy, Discovery and Innovation (Tokyo, Japan)
- Webinar: Q&A 1 to Q&A 5: Grant call: Strengthening no-fee open access publishing in Africa
- 7th OpenAIRE train-the-trainer Bootcamp (Online)

- No-fee OA publishing in Africa Community of Practice meeting (Online)
- Webinar: Research Assessment in Transition: Open Infrastructures, Policy and Diamond Open Access
- Uganda National Workshop on Open Science for National Development (Online)
- Webinar: Secondary Publication Rights — new EIFL provision
- Webinar: OJS: Best practices from Masaryk University and Open Monograph Press

JUNE

- The DIAMAS project General Assembly (Online)
- 9th International PhD Summer School (Palanga, Lithuania)
- Conference: Advancing Responsible Research Assessment in the Digital Space: A dialogue on ethics, integrity and open infrastructures for research in the AI era (Brussels, Belgium)
- The DIAMAS project Final Conference: The Future of Diamond Open Access Publishing in Europe and Beyond (Brussels, Belgium)
- Open science trainers meet-up (Online)
- User Rights Symposium 2025: Principles for Progress in Digital Copyright (Online)
- No-fee OA publishing in Africa Community of Practice meeting (Online)
- Webinar on Paper Mills, for Ukrainian research stakeholders
- Internet Governance Forum (Online)
- European Commission webinar for libraries: Understanding copyright

- E-Library and Zotero reference management software training for students and teachers at the National University of Laos Faculty of Law and Political Science (Online)
- EIFL-PLIP T-break: Navigating the Truth Online (Online)
- DIAMAS Regional Workshop: Visibility, Collaboration and Training for editors & publishers of open access journals (Online)

JULY

- Webinar: OJS: Best practices from Ethiopia and Slovenia
- Conference: Open Science: Monitoring Progress, Assessing Impact (Online)
- Webinar: Connect with the European Diamond OA Community: The Forum & Registry of the European Diamond Capacity Hub
- Open science trainers meet-up (Online)
- Workshop: Inclusive Open Science — From Global Asymmetries to Pluriversal Design (Online)
- Webinar: Information Literacy Mailbag
- No-fee OA publishing in Africa Community of Practice meeting (Online)
- Zotero reference management software training for students at the National University of Laos Faculty of Law and Political Science (Online)
- EIFL-PLIP T-break: Telling Our Stories Online: Experience of building the Malawi Folktales and Folksongs Database (Online)
- Internet Governance Forum webinar: Gaming & Gamification
- Webinar: AI and Copyright: What Authors and Libraries Need to Know about the Bartz v. Anthropic and Kadrey v. Meta Cases
- APAN60: The 60th Asia Pacific Advanced Network Conference (Online)

AUGUST

- Open science trainers meet-up (Online)

- No-fee OA publishing in Africa Community of Practice meeting (Online)
- DIAMAS Conversation: From Platform to Practice: Using the EDCH Training Platform to build national and institutional capacity (Online)
- AJOL webinar: Paper Mills
- Public Library Association webinar: Utilizing Outcome Measurement to Improve Library Services

SEPTEMBER

- WIPO webinar: Quantifying Impact: Strategies for Monitoring and Evaluating Technical Assistance and Capacity Building
- Digital Learning @ Ghana Public Libraries project stakeholder forum (Accra, Ghana)
- EIFL-Ukraine partnership meeting: A new stage of cooperation and development (Online)
- Open science trainers meet-up (Online)
- PUBMET 2025 Conference (Zagreb, Croatia)
- No-fee OA publishing in Africa Community of Practice meeting (Online)
- OpenAIRE A.M.K.E. General Assembly (Online)
- Kharkiv International Legal Forum: Open Science and Research Assessment: Legal Aspects (Online)
- Portuguese Open Science train-the-trainer Bootcamp (Coimbra, Portugal)
- 2025 EIFL General Assembly (Yerevan, Armenia)

OCTOBER

- ASSAf Discussion on Journal Special Issues and Guest Editorships (Online)
- SCANUL-ECS webinar: Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Information Services
- No-fee OA publishing in Africa Community of Practice meeting (Online)
- Open science trainers meet-up (Online)

- Consortium of Ugandan University Libraries 4th Annual Research Dissemination Conference (Online)
- Consultations on Institutional Open Science Policies and Publishing Regulations in Serbia (Online)
- Webinar: Retaining author's rights to enable open access to research outputs in Latvia
- Open Access Week (Online)
- Webinar: Open access and open science: Guidelines for publishing and applying for research grants in Ukraine
- OSICU 2025 Conference (Online)
- Webinar: Best Practices for No-Fee Open Access Journals in Latin America
- Botswana librarians forum: Equitable access and affordability (Online)
- Webinar: Publication Opportunities for Scientists in Kyrgyzstan
- 1st Diamond OA Policy Forum (Online)
- Botswana Open University International Open Week Commemoration (Online)

NOVEMBER

- Webinar: Diamond Discovery Hub
- Webinar: Managing OJS through containers
- Open science trainers meet-up (Online)
- New trends in non-profit scholarly publishing workshop (Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina)
- Open4UA Project training course: 'Peer Review in the Era of Open and Reproducible Science: New Challenges and Opportunities' (Online)
- Meeting of Internet Society Foundation's SCILLS grantees in Ghana (Online)
- EC TAIEX expert mission on Ukraine's National Open Science Plan (Online)
- Conference: Open science and the infrastructure of scientific information in Albania (Online)
- No-fee OA publishing in Africa Community of Practice meeting (Online)

- Workshop: Copyright Compliance in Education and the Role of Collective Management (Online)
- E-Library training for teachers and students at the National University of Laos Faculty of Law and Political Science (Vientiane, Laos)
- Webinar: OJS: Copyright metadata, multilingualism, preservation, reviewer credits and ISSN
- Webinar: OJS: Making sense of journal statistics
- Webinar: Boost the uptake of ROR ID in Malawi!

DECEMBER

- Open Access Week in Côte d'Ivoire (Online)
- 12th Baltic Librarians' Congress (Kaunas, Lithuania)
- WIPO Copyright Committee (47th Session) (Geneva, Switzerland)
- Open science trainers meet-up (Online)
- Webinar: OJS: Best practices and use cases in Portugal
- Internet Society Foundation's Africa SCILLS Grantee meeting (Dakar, Senegal)
- African Public and Community Libraries Virtual Summit 2025
- EIFL-PLIP T-break: Building public librarians' capacity for project development (Online)
- Conference: Europe-Africa Research Cooperation and Open Science (Brussels, Belgium)
- ALMASI project webinar: Reclaiming knowledge: Why Diamond Open Access matters
- 8th OpenAIRE train-the-trainer Bootcamp (Online)
- No-fee OA publishing in Africa Community of Practice meeting (Online)

KEY

- Training, workshops and events organized and/or supported by EIFL
- Presentations given by EIFL staff or partners
- Conferences and events attended by EIFL staff

OUR PARTNERS

EIFL has built relationships with a wide range of organizations to increase access to knowledge. In 2025, we worked with the following partners:

- Aarhus Public Libraries
- Access to Knowledge (A2K) Coalition
- African Journals Online (AJOL)
- African Library and Information Associations and Institutions (AfLIA)
- Arab States Research and Education Network (ASREN)
- ASEAN Public Libraries Information Network (APLiN)
- Association of Lithuanian Municipal Public Libraries
- Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI)
- Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)
- Coalition Publi.ca
- COMMUNIA Association
- Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR)
- Copyright for Creativity
- Creative Commons
- Crossref
- DataCite
- Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
- DSpace Community Advisory Team (DCAT), Lyris
- Education International
- European Union Intellectual Property Office
- Fundación Karisma
- Geneva Centre for Knowledge Governance (GCKG)
- Ghana Library Authority
- Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS)
- Harvard Open Access Project (HOAP)
- HIFA2020: Healthcare Information For All by 2020
- International Coalition of Library Consortia (ICOLC)
- International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA)
- Kenya National Library Service
- Knowledge Rights 21
- LIBER
- Library Copyright Alliance (LCA)
- LIBSENSE
- Lithuanian Audiosensory Library
- Namibia Library and Archives Service
- National Institute of Informatics of Japan
- National Library of Armenia
- National Library of Uganda
- National Library Service of Malawi
- Networked Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (NDLTD)
- Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA)
- OA Switchboard
- OpenAIRE AMKE
- Open Data and Intellectual Property Institute (ODIPI)
- OA2020
- Public Knowledge Project (PKP)
- Research Organization Registry (ROR)
- Sorbonne Université
- SPARC
- SPARC Europe
- Tangible Africa / Leva Foundation
- TechSoup
- UbuntuNet Alliance
- UKSG
- UNESCO
- University of Washington, Information School, USA
- West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN)
- World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO)
- Zambia Library Service

KEY

- EIFL is a founding member/signatory
- EIFL is a member
- EIFL staff are board or committee members
- Official relations (including MoU)
- Working Relationship

In addition, EIFL collaborated with 53 partners through European Commission-funded projects: Aligning and Mutualizing Nonprofit OA Publishing Services Internationally (ALMASI), Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication (DIAMAS) and Open Science for Ukrainian Higher Education System (Open4UA).

WHERE WE WORK

In 2025, EIFL worked in partnership with library consortia in 36 countries. We have also run projects in an additional 24 countries where we do not have library consortia.

■ **PARTNER COUNTRIES** are countries where we have a formal agreement with the national library consortium. EIFL partner consortia work with all EIFL programmes.

■ **PROJECT COUNTRIES** are countries in which we have worked with libraries on specific projects.

STAY CONNECTED

[eifl.net](https://www.eifl.net)

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For more information about EIFL and our work visit [eifl.net](https://www.eifl.net)